

IRRIGATION OF GOOSE BY WATER-SAVING METHOD

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Annotation: This article is mainly written about the distinct advantages and disadvantages of resurstejamkor irrigation technologies in Goose irrigation. It is also written that the economy of Water Resources will be if drip irrigation works are carried out.

Keywords: irrigation, norm, mineral, fertilizer, resource, range, productivity.

Along with the increasing demand for water resources in many parts of the world, including our country, the shortage of water is also increasing year by year. Bunda has a deep sense of water shortage, especially its consumers, which are located at the bottom of rivers and away from the canal and other water sources. Increasing the amount of harvest from irrigated areas on the basis of economical and effective use of Water Resources in the Republic, expanding the production of food products in this regard, effective work is carried out to further improve the living standards of the country's population by improving its quality and filling the domestic market. In the following years, a large-scale work is carried out on the effective and targeted use of water in our republic.

Serious attention is paid to raising the culture of water use under the leadership of our esteemed compatriot, accelerating reforms in the water economy, strengthening the material and technical base of the sphere. Extensive work is being carried out on advanced methods of irrigation of crops, including the introduction of drip irrigation technology

In the drip irrigation system, the technology of caring for the soil includes the following basic indicators: the use of high-yielding and fast-growing varieties

suitable for different soil climatic conditions, the rational system of processing between the main, hay-picked and row to the soil, the planting of high-quality seeds, the stratification of mineral fertilizers, the system of fully automating the, spraying and defoliation with the help of gauze, harvesting cotton with the help of machines. This technology is actually adopted and is compatible with irrigation technology through a widely used rut. The main difference of the drip irrigation system is that during the growing season, a certain part of the mineral fertilizers and herbicides are allowed to be combined with irrigation to the plant, and not processed in a row.

The soil of the experimental area is a medium sand, the depth of groundwater is 1,5-1,7 meters, during the period of application of porous growth is 1,6-1,9 meters and is less saline. According to the results of the experiment, the drip irrigation system has some advantages over raked irrigation, the economy of 45-50% of irrigation water, as well as mineral fertilizer 40-50% were determined from the research. It was also determined that the number of processing between rows decreased by 2,75 Times, water consumption to 1 m³/ha for the cultivation of cotton crop to 85 s/Ha.

From the agrophysical properties of the soil in drip-irrigated fields: lightening of the bulk weight, improved water permeability were observed. It was also determined that harmful, water-soluble salts accumulate poorly in the root-dispersed layer, the absorption of nutrients by the plant due to the dissolution of mineral fertilizers by water increases and the increase in the yield elements. Productivity increased to 7,4 s/M when drip irrigation was observed. In addition, the process of salinity in the soil, on account of the constant retention of moisture in the drip-watered areas, did not suffer from wilt disease, creating a very small amount.

Experiments on the development of an optimal irrigation and feeding procedure for drip irrigation of the goose were carried out in the areas where it was previously watered. In the experiments, humidifying pipes with a length of 170 meters, laid to each owner, with a maximum slope of 0,015, with a large slope, were installed along the slope of the maximum slope of the slope of 0,006, which was

ploughed in the first year after the three-year bed, as well as humidifying pipes with a length of 60.

Experience system

Options	Irrigation method	Irrigation took moisture of the soil, compared to CHDNS, %,	Annual norm of mineral fertilizers, in kg/ ha
1	through rut (control)	70-75-70	N240, P170, K120,
2	Drip irrigation system	70-75-70	N240, P170, K120,
3	Drip irrigation system	70-75-65	N240, P170, K120,
4	Drip irrigation system	70-80-65	N240, P170, K120,

Experiment areas were grown with medium-coarse mechanical content, medium – fiber Steam-6 grade of porous in the range of 60 cm, humidifier-pipes based on Izroil technology were delivered 1,2 meters from the rear of the tractor. In experiments, the goose was planted in 4 rows, each option (delyanka) in 8 variants.

All field and laboratory studies were conducted on the former Uzbek methodological manuals. In the Haydov layer (0-30 CM), the volume weight of the soil is 1.38-1.41 g/cm³, while in the haydov layer (30-50 cm) this indicator is slightly increased to 1.49-1.58 g/cm³, the relative weight and total porosity indicators are 3.14-3.21 g/cm³ and 51.3-47.1% respectively in these layers.

The hydrophysical parameters of the soil are as follows, the limited field moisture capacity (CHDNS) in 0-100 CM part of the soil layer is 20,3-21,4, the natural moisture content is 17,2-18,5% in the hay layer, and in the subsurface layer is 18,3-20,8 %. The order of irrigation of the porous is formed due to the amount of moisture received from the irrigation set in the experimental system and the approximate layer of soil 0-50 CM. The data obtained indicate the high efficiency

of drip irrigation compared to irrigation through the rut. In particular, if brutto water is spent on seasonal 6300 m³/h in irrigation through the rut, we can observe that in drip irrigation water is spent on 2 and 3 variants to 2730 m³/h, and in the fourth variant (70-80-65) to a total of 2980 m³/h in the norm. Thus, in the order of 70-75-70% of drip irrigation, 57% of water is economized, in the order of 70-80-65% of drip irrigation.

Drip irrigation system should ensure that the entire part of the watering hole is moistened in one tekist. Such humidification creates conditions for the uniform operation of the droppers when the pressure is ensured only by the presence of a certain indicator (1,0-4,0 atm) in the head part of the water supply pipes to the field.

It is required to keep the system in constant control to prevent a well developed malfunction. As a result of cracks and malfunctions, which can lead to a decrease in the pressure in the closed system, it is necessary to quickly fix the areas where the gearing is disrupted and the water flows in the hopper. During irrigation, the filters that hold large and small particles in the water must be cleaned and washed current. If necessary, watering pipes are also washed. To do this, the plugs at the end of all the pipes are removed and the water from the outlet is drained through the throwing arc. It should always be checked that the irrigation pipes are correctly located between the rut, on the soil of the Waterproofers.

Conclusion:

The features of agrotechnical care using new technology drip irrigation systems with intensive prospects for porcine and crops entering its complex in the conditions of old irrigated Meadow Marsh soils are described above. The high efficiency obtained in these experiments in the field of water saving has also proved itself positive in terms of the environment. Productivity increased to 7,4 s/M when drip irrigation was observed. In addition, the process of salinity in the soil, on account of the constant retention of moisture in the drip-watered areas, did not suffer from wilt disease, creating a very small amount.

Meadow Marsh soils are widely distributed in the region, along with irrational erosion and flowing water, the mine is washed into the waters of Oghuz.

Therefore, first of all, it is desirable to build a drip irrigation system on the territory of self-soil, where the surface of the groundwater is located.

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